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Supplement of

Anthropogenic and catchment characteristic signatures in the water quality of Swiss rivers: a quantitative assessment

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22 **S1. The impact of detection thresholds on the results**

23 The NADUF data are collected following the ISO/EN methods for water analysis. Uncertainties in the data may
24 rise due to the detection limits of the instruments or analysis methods. The specifics of the data collection
25 methods including also the detection limits are reported at the following link:

26 https://www.bafu.admin.ch/dam/bafu/en/dokumente/hydrologie/fachinfo-daten/naduf-methoden-chemische-analysen-eawag-2018.pdf.download.pdf/Methoden_NADUF_2018_E.pdf

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28 The differences in concentration magnitude across catchments are higher than the sensitivity of the instruments
29 and therefore are significant.

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33 **Figure S1:** Discharge seasonality. Each point represents the monthly average discharge normalized by the average
34 discharge over the monitoring period, while the red dashed line is the average normalized discharge over the entire
35 monitoring period. Blue upper box: Swiss Plateau catchments. Light blue middle box: hybrid catchments. Yellow
36 bottom box: Alpine catchments. The hydrological regimes are clustered according to the main categories reported
37 by Weingartner and Aschwanden, 1992.

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54 **Figure S2:** Long-term solutes trends. Each line represents the monthly average concentration of each solute. The
55 color bar indicates the years of the monitoring period, from the first year (blue) to the last year (red). The
56 presented figure refers to the Rhine catchment at the monitoring section of Rekingen.

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62 **Figure S3.** Monthly average of discharge (black) and solute load (blue) normalized by the average of the entire
 63 monitoring period. The red horizontal line represents the reference value 1 (i.e., mean). The subpanel (a) refers
 64 to Calcium and subpanel (b) to Nitrate. Calcium is originated by rock weathering and it mostly follows the
 65 seasonality of discharge. Nitrate, instead, is strongly related to the anthropic activities and in the most impacted
 66 catchments (i.e. Thur, Aare – Brugg) the load has a seasonality, which is different from the seasonality of
 67 discharge.

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70 **Figure S4.** Molar Na:Cl ratio across catchments. Catchments with higher inhabitant density (AN, BR, RE, WM,
 71 HA, CH) show molar ratio between Na^+ and Cl^- close to 1, while catchments with lower human presence (PO,
 72 DI, SA) show higher values. Lümpepenbach and Erlenbach catchments show very high molar Na:Cl ratio, as the
 73 number of their inhabitants is 0 and deicing salt is not used.

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76 **Figure S5.** Suspended solids concentrations across the catchments. The boxplot shows the suspended solid
 77 concentrations across the eleven catchments, ordered from the Swiss Plateau (blue background), to the hybrid
 78 (light blue background) and Alpine (yellow background) catchments. The Alpine catchments show much higher
 79 concentrations and variability.

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82 **Figure S6.** Examples of C-Q relations. The patterns of the linear C-Q relation of some solutes (Mg^{2+} , H_4SiO_4 ,
 83 NO_3 and TOC) are plotted in a log-log space. Orange points and line refer to the Swiss Plateau catchment Thur
 84 (AN), while green ones refer to the Alpine catchment Inn (SA). The variability of concentrations for all the
 85 solutes across all the catchments is a few orders of magnitude less than the variability of discharge.

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88 **Figure S7.** Ratios of DRP/TP in time across four different catchments. The red dashed line represents the
 89 average value of the DRP/TP ratio computed on the entire monitoring period. All the selected catchments show
 90 significant decrease of DRP/TP ratio in time.

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92 **Table S1.** Spearman's correlation coefficient between (a) the median concentrations of each solute, (b) the b
 93 exponent for low-flows and (c) the b exponent for high-flows across the catchments with some catchment

(b) b exponent inf												
	Ca²⁺	Mg²⁺	Na⁺	H₄SiO₄	K⁺	Cl⁻	NO₃	TN	DRP	TP	DOC	TOC
Catchment area	0.51	0.54	-0.14	0.17	-0.09	-0.21	-0.28	-0.17	-0.20	-0.14	-0.22	0.15
Average altitude	-0.72	-0.63	-0.24	-0.40	-0.16	-0.46	-0.49	-0.43	-0.26	0.24	-0.25	0.33
Mean annual precipitation	0.01	-0.10	0.04	0.15	0.16	0.42	0.58	0.44	0.58	0.48	0.34	0.07
Mean annual discharge	-0.57	-0.40	0.14	-0.27	0.45	0.24	0.27	0.23	0.41	0.62	0.33	0.49
Lake area	0.55	0.58	0.08	0.18	-0.04	-0.08	-0.40	-0.25	-0.28	-0.25	-0.28	-0.11
% of Swiss Plateau area	0.68	0.49	-0.03	0.49	-0.18	0.09	0.10	0.06	0.18	-0.19	0.22	-0.16
% of Alpine area	-0.56	-0.32	0.17	-0.32	0.25	-0.08	-0.05	-0.02	-0.11	0.34	0.02	0.38
% of intensive agricultural area	0.76	0.48	-0.05	0.51	-0.19	0.14	0.13	0.07	0.18	-0.28	0.05	-0.28
% of extensive agricultural area	-0.75	-0.48	0.08	-0.52	0.44	0.12	0.10	0.13	0.24	0.44	0.45	0.45
Inhabitants density	0.70	0.53	-0.13	0.48	-0.38	-0.13	-0.07	-0.20	-0.19	-0.37	-0.17	-0.18

94 characteristics listed in the first column. The green cells represent the significant correlations, i.e., the
95 correlations characterized by a p value lower than the significance threshold α fixed at 0.05.

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(a) Median solute concentration												
	Ca²⁺	Mg²⁺	Na⁺	H₄SiO₄	K⁺	Cl⁻	NO₃	TN	DRP	TP	DOC	TOC
Catchment area	0.36	-0.03	0.37	0.38	-0.38	0.18	0.27	0.33	0.18	0.04	0.54	0.51
Average altitude	-0.64	-0.55	-0.67	-0.73	-0.08	-0.63	-0.78	-0.75	-0.75	-0.54	-0.32	-0.41
Mean annual precipitation	-0.05	0.00	-0.01	-0.02	0.15	0.11	0.12	0.05	0.15	0.17	-0.34	-0.35
Mean annual discharge	-0.69	-0.54	-0.65	-0.72	-0.28	-0.57	-0.66	-0.67	-0.58	-0.51	-0.33	-0.43
Lake area	0.45	-0.13	0.09	0.19	-0.24	0.02	0.09	0.12	-0.02	-0.19	0.42	0.30
% of Swiss Plateau area	0.83	0.63	0.83	0.85	0.25	0.73	0.91	0.91	0.80	0.63	0.42	0.51
% of Alpine area	-0.75	-0.44	-0.70	-0.77	0.03	-0.63	-0.83	-0.83	-0.74	-0.57	-0.22	-0.35
% of intensive agricultural area	0.88	0.38	0.78	0.87	-0.15	0.68	0.85	0.87	0.78	0.58	0.54	0.63
% of extensive agricultural area	-0.81	-0.35	-0.58	-0.68	-0.18	-0.52	-0.63	-0.64	-0.52	-0.41	-0.49	-0.52
Inhabitants density	0.77	0.40	0.70	0.72	0.05	0.57	0.67	0.69	0.56	0.40	0.55	0.57

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(c) b exponent sup												
	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	H ₄ SiO ₄	K ⁺	Cl ⁻	NO ₃	TN	DRP	TP	DOC	TOC
Catchment area	0.78	0.59	0.21	0.13	-0.12	-0.40	-0.17	0.16	-0.35	0.09	0.03	0.50
Average altitude	-0.69	-0.77	-0.28	-0.53	-0.75	-0.40	-0.53	-0.18	-0.28	0.30	-0.29	-0.04
Mean annual precipitation	-0.14	0.01	-0.53	0.10	0.40	0.24	0.37	0.06	0.35	-0.41	0.30	-0.35
Mean annual discharge	-0.62	-0.63	-0.65	-0.43	-0.25	0.01	-0.06	0.03	0.05	-0.18	-0.02	-0.38
Lake area	0.67	0.56	0.49	0.01	-0.15	-0.28	-0.38	0.03	-0.53	-0.19	-0.05	0.28
% of Swiss Plateau area	0.72	0.74	0.41	0.48	0.47	0.15	0.38	0.47	0.23	-0.02	0.70	0.30
% of Alpine area	-0.59	-0.62	-0.21	-0.35	-0.46	-0.11	-0.31	0.04	-0.13	0.22	-0.22	-0.02
% of intensive agricultural area	0.79	0.75	0.27	0.47	0.42	0.00	0.24	0.36	0.13	-0.09	0.59	0.29
% of extensive agricultural area	-0.76	-0.76	-0.45	-0.53	-0.20	0.19	0.09	0.21	0.24	-0.02	0.02	-0.53
Inhabitants density	0.77	0.73	0.33	0.40	0.11	-0.28	-0.07	0.21	-0.18	0.03	0.41	0.56

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104 **Table S2.** Monthly trend analysis: results of Mann- Kendall test on a monthly basis. The significant trends are
 105 highlighted with the grey boxes and the sign +/- refers respectively to positive or negative trends, while the dark-
 106 to-light blue refers to the gradient of intensive agriculture in the basins (Table 1). Tables a) refer to solutes that
 107 showed clear increasing or decreasing trend in the long-term trend analysis. Tables b) refer to solutes that
 108 showed a non-monotonic trend, while Tables c) include solutes that did not show any clear trend in the long-
 109 term.

110 a)

		AN	BR	VW	RE	HA	LU	CH	DI	PO	SA	ER														
Na ⁺	Jan		+		+	+		+	+	+			Cl ⁻	Jan	+		-	+	+		+	+	+			
	Feb		+		+	+		+	+	+				Feb	+	+		+	+		+	+	+		-	
	Mar		+		+	+		+	+	+				Mar	+	+		+	+		+	+	+		+	-
	Apr		+		+		-	+	+	+				Apr	+	-	+		+	+		+	+	+		
	May		+											May	+	-	+		+							
	Jun		+				+			+				Jun	+				+							
	Jul		+							+				Jul	+											
	Aug		+							+				Aug	+											
	Sep		+									+		+	Sep								+	+		
	Oct											+			Oct										+	
	Nov														Nov										+	
	Dec		+		+	+				+	+				Dec	+			+	+	+	+	+	+		
DRP	Jan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	TP	Jan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Feb	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		Feb	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Mar	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		Mar	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Apr	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		Apr	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	May	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		May	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
	Jun	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		Jun	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	
	Jul	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-		Jul	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	+		
	Aug	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+		-	Aug	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+			
	Sep	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		-	Sep	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+			
	Oct	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		-	Oct	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Nov	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		-	Nov	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Dec	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		-	Dec	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

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112 b)

		AN	BR	VW	RE	HA	LU	CH	DI	PO	SA	ER			AN	BR	VW	RE	HA	LU	CH	DI	PO	SA	ER	
Mg²⁺	Jan			+	+	+	-			+	-	-	TN	Jan	-	-	-	-	-							
	Feb		+	+	+	+		+						Feb	-	-	-	-	-							
	Mar		+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+				Mar	-	-	-	-	-							
	Apr				+	+			+		+			Apr	-	-	-	-	-							
	May			+	+	+				-				May	-	-	-	-	-							
	Jun			+	+	+			+					Jun		-	-	-	-							
	Jul			+	+	+			+					Jul					+	-						
	Aug			+	+	+			+					Aug												
	Sep			+	+	+	+		+	+	+	+		Sep												
	Oct		+	+	+	+	+		+		+	+		Oct		+		+	+		+					
	Nov			+	+	+	+		+		+			Nov	+	+		+	+		+	+				
	Dec			+										Dec												
K⁺	Jan		+			+	+	-	+	+	+		TOC	Jan			-		-							
	Feb		+	+		+	+	-	+	+	+			Feb	-	-	-	-	-							
	Mar				+	+			+	+	+			Mar	-	-	-	-	-							
	Apr				+	+			+	+	+			Apr												
	May				+	+			+	+	+			May												
	Jun		+	+		+			+	+	+			Jun		+										
	Jul			+		+			+	+	+			Jul												
	Aug				+	+			+	+	+			Aug												
	Sep				+	+			+	+	+			Sep			+	+		+	+	+				
	Oct				+	+	+		+	+	+			Oct			+	+	+	+	+	+				
	Nov				+	+	+		+	+	+			Nov			+	+	+	+	+	+				
	Dec				+				+					Dec			+	+	+	+	+	+				

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114 c)

		AN	BR	VW	RE	HA	LU	CH	DI	PO	SA	ER			AN	BR	VW	RE	HA	LU	CH	DI	PO	SA	ER	
Ca²⁺	Jan								+				H₄SiO₄	Jan			+		+							
	Feb													Feb												
	Mar													Mar												
	Apr													Apr												
	May													May												
	Jun													Jun												
	Jul													Jul												
	Aug													Aug												
	Sep													Sep												
	Oct													Oct												
	Nov													Nov												
	Dec													Dec												
NO₃	Jan								+	+	+		DOC	Jan					+	+	-			+		
	Feb											Feb														
	Mar											Mar														
	Apr											Apr														
	May											May														
	Jun											Jun														
	Jul											Jul														
	Aug											Aug														
	Sep											Sep														
	Oct											Oct														
	Nov											Nov														
	Dec											Dec														

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